

PROTECTION OF ALIMONY RIGHTS OF MINOR CHILDREN DURING DIVORCE

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Annotation: *This article discusses the issue of protecting the rights of minor children in family legal relations, in particular during divorce. In particular, the current legislation on regulating alimony relations of minor children during divorce and the problems associated with them were examined, and ways to improve them were proposed.*

Key words: *divorce, minors, child, personal non-property relations, property rights.*

In the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Guarantees of Children’s Rights” and a number of other legal documents relating to family relations specifically address issues of financial support and upbringing of minor children.

Our Constitution places responsibility for the upbringing and education of children on every father and mother. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure that divorce does not affect the rights and interests of children, and even if it does, their rights must be fully protected and additional guarantees must be created for them. Personal non-property relations between children and parents arise from a single legal fact - the birth of a child¹.

Dissolution of marriage by husband and wife definitely affects the property

¹ Инамджанова Г.С. Ота-оналар ва болаларнинг ҳуқуқларини оила ҳуқуқий ҳимоя қилиш муаммолари. – Т.: 2005. – Б 133.

and personal non-property rights of minor children. That is, it threatens the child's ability to exercise their rights in practice. The danger of the child's rights and interests arises when the husband and wife are on the verge of divorce or divorce.

Child support from parents can take many forms. In particular, it is possible to receive maintenance through the provision of food, clothing, or in the form of money, that is, through alimony. Of course, the most traditional of these forms of maintenance and the one that appears to everyone when they think of maintenance is receiving maintenance in the form of alimony.

Property rights between parents and children include alimony obligations. Aliment – Latin alimentum - means “food”, “maintenance”, “funds for support” and is a material thing that one person is forced to pay to another person.²

In most legal literature, most scholars consider maintenance as alimony, while other categories of scholars recognize alimony as a form of maintenance.

Y.F.Bespalov lists the different sides of the two above concepts: alimony may not satisfy even the most basic needs of the child, and the provision may deviate from the content of the most necessary types of assistance (food, clothing, school supplies). He mentions that mandatory alimony is only money, which means that its amount is small and, as mentioned above, is not always sufficient to meet the needs of the child.³

In our opinion, as we noted above, “maintenance” is a broader concept, and alimony is a form of maintenance, and non-monetary items and items that provide various benefits in kind can be collected as maintenance. Collection of alimony in the form of the goods is possible mainly upon reaching a mediation agreement between husband and wife.

² Абдурахмонова Х.Б. Ота-она ва болалар алимент ҳуқуқлари ва мажбуриятларининг коллизия тартибга солиниши. – Т.: ТДЮИ., 2015. – Б 12.

³ Беспалов Ю.Ф. Защита гражданских и семейных прав ребенка в Российской Федерации. Учебно-практическое пособие. – М.: Ось-89, 2004. – Б 109.

When it comes to the right of children to receive maintenance from their father or mother, we can see below that this relationship has caused several arguments and debates.

Our current legislation stipulates that a husband and wife can make an agreement on the payment of alimony in the event of a future divorce.

Kh.B.Abdurakhmonova states that “alimony is considered a family legal relationship and is defined as the amount of money that one family member is forced to pay to another family member according to a court decision or mutual agreement.”⁴

In our opinion, relations related to alimony obligations are purely family legal relations, and property relations are not only related to civil legal relations, but also include labor legal relations, and just as labor law is a separate branch of law, family legal relations have their own uniqueness. In addition, there are blood-kinship ties between the subjects of family-legal relations, and relations between them arise on the basis of mutual inner feelings.

At this point, the question arises, if the child is also a member of the family, then the alimony paid to the child will not be added to the joint property of the husband and wife, or the property of the child is not considered joint property?

In this regard, according to the opinion of scientists, in particular, Professor O.Okyulov writes that it is appropriate to include a clause on the private property of children in the family in Article 93 of the Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As a confirmation of his opinion, the professor approves that T.V.Belova’s proposal to the laws that alimony paid or collected for minors or disabled children and the goods and things purchased at their expense belong to them on the basis of property rights is appropriate.⁵

⁴ Абдурахмонова Х.Б. Ота-она ва болалар алимент ҳуқуқлари ва мажбуриятларининг коллизия тартибга солиниши. – Т.: ТДЮИ, 2015. – Б 11

⁵ Ўша жойда.

We also partially agree with the above opinions, and we believe that after the divorce of the husband and wife, it is necessary to pay special attention to the issue of children's private property. The reason is that a child growing up between a husband and a wife who is not separated from marriage is raised by his parents who worry about his material well-being. However, child support relationships begin to become problematic once the husband and wife actually start living separately. Although this is sad, it should be said that if a father (mother), who pretended to be kind before the divorce, after the divorce, the ex-wife (husband) goes to court with an application to collect alimony for the material maintenance of the child, some ex-husbands actually reduce their income in order to pay less alimony, even his real income is enough, they will intentionally apply for employment documents in enterprises or organizations with low monthly wages.

However, the divorce of a husband and wife should not affect the financial support of the child and should not violate their rights in this regard.

As we explained above, child support payments, which are considered a form of child support rights after divorce, are one of the personal rights that serve to financially support a child until he or she reaches adulthood.

Consequently, alimony is the mutual property rights of family members, which are personal in nature and determined by strict laws.⁶

From this point of view, we consider it appropriate to guarantee the rights of the minor children of the husband and wife even after a divorce, by supplementing Article 93 of the current Family Code with the following paragraph 5, which is a norm related to the private property of children:

“Alimony payments or other forms of maintenance paid by the spouse or one of them to their minor children during the period when the husband and wife lived together in marriage, or during the period of their divorce, until the children

⁶ Абдурахмонова Х.Б. Ота-она ва болалар алимент ҳуқуқлари ва мажбуриятларининг коллизия тартибга солиниши. – Т.: ТДЮИ, 2015. – Б 12.

reach adulthood, are the private property of the children.”

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